

A PVDF-based Flexible energy harvester from human motion

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Abstract:

Energy harvesting is the way of converting ambient vibration and human motion into electrical energy that can be used to power other device, such as safety monitoring, wearable electronics and medical implants. Recently, with the widespread use of wearable electronics, Flexible piezoelectric energy harvesting approaches have received both considerable industrial and academic interest. However, the fragile PZT materials and insufficient output power become key constraint on realizing the flexible piezoelectric energy generating from long cycle human motion. This paper investigates a design and modeling methods for flexible piezoelectric energy harvesting from human motions. A detailed fabrication process of PVDF-based vibration energy harvesters is discussed for performance enhancement in human motion. Numerical simulation and experimental verification are performed to demonstrate the preferable performance for energy harvesting from human motion.